

1 **Split-QF system for fine-tuned transgene expression in *Drosophila***

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16

17 **Abstract**

18 The Q-system is a binary expression system that works well across species. Here we report
19 the development and demonstrate applications of a split-QF system that drives strong
20 expression in *Drosophila*, is repressible by QS and inducible by a small non-toxic molecule
21 quinic acid. The split-QF system is fully compatible with existing split-GAL4 and split-LexA
22 lines, thus greatly expanding the range of possible advanced intersectional experiments and
23 anatomical, physiological and behavioural assays in *Drosophila* and in other organisms.

24

25 **Introduction**

26 Binary expression systems GAL4/UAS (Brand and Perrimon 1993), LexA/LexAop (Lai and Lee
27 2006) and the Q-system (Potter *et al.* 2010; Riabinina *et al.* 2015; Riabinina and Potter 2016)
28 allow labelling and functional manipulation of genetically defined subsets of cells in
29 *Drosophila*. Several methods have been developed in order to limit expression of effectors
30 to small specific subsets of cells (Golic and Lindquist 1989; Lee and Luo 1999; Luan *et al.*
31 2006; Tirian and Dickson 2017). One of these methods, the split-GAL4 system (Luan *et al.*
32 2006; Tirian and Dickson 2017; Dionne *et al.* 2018), directs expression of a GAL4 DNA-

33 binding domain (DBD) independently of a GAL4 activation domain (AD). A fully functional
34 GAL4 is reconstituted only where the expression patterns of both subsets overlap. In
35 practice, GAL4AD is often too weak and is replaced by p65AD or VP16AD to boost strength
36 of expression (Tirian and Dickson 2017; Dionne *et al.* 2018).

37 We reasoned that, since the QF2/QF2^w (a weaker version of QF2, with a mutated C-terminal
38 (Riabinina *et al.* 2015)) transactivators of the Q-system are generally stronger than GAL4
39 (Riabinina *et al.* 2015), the split-QF system may function well in *Drosophila* by coupling
40 QFDBD and QFAD. This approach has been successfully tested in *C.elegans* (Wei *et al.* 2012),
41 but not characterised or used in *Drosophila*. The use of split-QF with QFAD would allow the
42 system to remain both repressible by QS and inducible by quinic acid (QA), in the same
43 manner as the original Q-system. We have also previously developed chimeric GAL4QF and
44 LexAQF transactivators (Riabinina *et al.* 2015), which indicated that QFAD and QF2^wAD are
45 likely to function with GAL4DBD and LexADBD domains when brought together by leucine
46 zippers.

47

48 **Materials and Methods**

49 **Molecular biology**

50 Plasmids were constructed by standard procedures including enzyme digestions, PCR and
51 subcloning, using the In-Fusion HD Cloning System CE, Takara Bio Europe # 639636. Plasmid
52 inserts were verified by DNA sequencing.

53 **nsyb-nls::QFAD::Zip+ construct**

- 54 1) pattB-QF2-hsp70 plasmid (Addgene #46115) was digested with Zral and EcoRI to
55 remove Kozak-QF2 sequence.
- 56 2) Kozak-nls sequence was PCR-amplified from pBPp65ADZpUw (Addgene #26234) with
57 primers *ATC GAC AGC CGA ATT CAA CAT GGA TAA AGC GGA ATT A* (forward) and
58 *ACG GTA TCG ATA GAC GTC CAA TTC GAC CTT TCT CTT C* (reverse).
- 59 3) The PCR product was cloned into the digested vector by InFusion cloning.
- 60 4) The cloning product was digested with Zral
- 61 5) QFAD sequence was PCR-amplified from pattB-QF2-hsp70 plasmid (Addgene
62 #46115) with primers *AAG GTC GAA TTG GAC GTC CGT CAG TTG GAG CTA A*
63 (forward) and *ACG GTA TCG ATA GAC AGA TCT CTG TTC GTA TGT ATT AAT GTC GGA*
64 *GAA G* (reverse)
- 65 6) The PCR product (5) was subcloned into (4) by InFusion cloning.
- 66 7) (6) was digested with BglII
- 67 8) The GGGGG-Zip+ sequence was PCR-amplified from pBPp65ADZpUw (Addgene
68 #26234) with primers *ATA CGA ACA GAG ATC TGG AGG AGG TGG TGG AGG* (forward)
69 and *ATC GAT AGA CAG ATC GGC CGG CCT TAC TTG CCG CCG CC* (reverse).
- 70 9) The PCR product (8) was subcloned into the digested vector (7) by InFusion cloning.
- 71 10) Product of (9) was digested with FseI and NotI to remove hsp70 terminator and to
72 replace it with SV40 terminator
- 73 11) SV40 terminator was PCR-amplified from UAS-LUC-UAS-eYFP plasmid(Lynd and Lycett
74 2012) with primers *GGC AAG TAA GGC CGG CCG ATC TTT GTG AAG GAA CCT TAC*
75 (forward) and *CCT CGA GCC GCG GCC GCG ATC CAG ACA TGA TAA GAT AC* (reverse).
- 76 12) The PCR product (11) was subcloned into the vector (10) by InFusion cloning.

77 *nsyb-nls::QF2^wAD::Zip+ construct*

- 78 1) The *nsyb-nls::QFAD::Zip+* construct was digested with BglII and Zral to remove QFAD.
79 2) QF2^wAD sequence was PCR amplified from from pattb-QF2-hsp70 (Addgene #46115)
80 with primers AAG GTC GAA TTG GAC GTC CGT CAG TTG GAG CTC C (forward) and
81 CAC CTC CTC CAG ATC TTT CTT CTT TTT GGT ATG TAT TAA TGT CGG AGA AGT TAC
82 ATC C (reverse)
83 3) The PCR product (2) was InFusino-cloned into (1).

84 *nsyb-nls::p65AD::Zip+ construct*

- 85 1) The *nsyb-nls::QFAD::Zip+* construct was digested with FseI and Zral to remove
86 QFAD::Zip+ sequence.
87 2) The p65AD::Zip+ sequence was PCR amplified from pBPp65ADZpUw (Addgene
88 #26234) with primers AAG GTC GAA TTG GAC GTC GGA TCC ACG CCG ATG (forward)
89 and CTT CAC AAA GAT CGG CCG GCC TTA CTT GCC GCC GCC (reverse).
90 3) The PCR product (3) was InFusion-subcloned into (1).

91 *nsyb-nls::GAL4AD::Zip+ construct*

- 92 1) The *nsyb-nls::QFAD::Zip+* construct was digested with BglII and Zral to remove QFAD.
93 2) The GAL4AD sequence was PCR amplified from pBPGAL4.2Uw-2 (Addgene #26227)
94 with primers AAG GTC GAA TTG GAC GTC GCC AAC TTC AAC CAG AGT GG (forward)
95 and CAC CTC CTC CAG ATC TCT CCT TCT TTG GGT TCG GTG (reverse).
96 3) The PCR product (3) was InFusion-subcloned into (1).

97

98 *nsyb-Zip-::QFDBD construct*

- 99 1) pattB-QF2-hsp70 plasmid (Addgene #46115) was digested with Zral and EcoRI to
100 remove Kozak-QF2 sequence.

- 101 2) Kozak-Zip⁻-GGGGGG sequence was PCR-amplified from pBPZpGAL4DBDUw (Addgene
102 #26233) with primers *ATC GAC AGC CGA ATT CAA CAT GCT GGA GAT CCG C* (forward)
103 and *ACG GTA TCG ATA GAC GTC ACC TCC ACC TCC ACC TCC* (reverse).
- 104 3) The PCR product (3) was InFusion-subcloned into (1).
- 105 4) (3) was digested with ZraI
- 106 5) QFDBD was PCR-amplified from pattB-QF2-hsp70 plasmid (Addgene #46115) with
107 primers *GGA GGT GGA GGT GAC GTC ATG CCA CCC AAG CG* (forward) and *ACG GTA*
108 *TCG ATA GAC GGC CGG CCT TAG AGG AGG CGG GTA ATG C* (reverse).
- 109 6) The PCR product (5) was InFusion-subcloned into (4).
- 110 7) (6) was digested with FseI and NotI to remove hsp70 terminator and to replace it
111 with SV40 terminator
- 112 8) SV40 terminator was PCR-amplified from UAS-LUC-UAS-eYFP plasmid(Lynd and Lycett
113 2012) with primers *CTC CTC TAA GGC CGG CCG ATC TTT GTG AAG GAA CCT TAC*
114 (forward) and *CCT CGA GCC GCG GCC GCG ATC CAG ACA TGA TAA GAT AC* (reverse).
- 115 9) The PCR product (8) was InFusion-subcloned into (7).

116

117 **Transgenic flies (new and existing)**

118 New transgenic lines were generated by inserting *nsyb-QFDBD* construct in attp40 (II) and all
119 *nsyb-AD* constructs into attp2 (III).

120 Other *Drosophila* stocks, used in this paper, were acquired from the Bloomington Stock
121 Centre (indicated by # below) or were in personal stocks of the authors.

122 Figure 1: QUAS-mCD8-GFP (#30003), tub-QS (#52112), *nsyb-QF2* (attp2, personal stocks,
123 OR), *nsyb-QF2^w* (#51960), QUAS-Ppyr/Luc (#64773);

124 Figure 2: UAS-mCD8-GFP (personal stocks, OR), elav-GAL4DBD (derived from #23868),
125 VT019838-GAL4DBD (#75177), ChAT-GAL4DBD (#60318), UAS-Luc (#64774) , 13xLexAop2-
126 mCD8-GFP (#32204) , VT007395-ZpLexADBD (personal stocks, B.J.D.), VT009847-ZpLexADBD
127 (personal stocks, B.J.D.);

128 Figure 3: nsyb-LexAQF (#51953), 13xLexAop2-KZip+ (#76253), VGlut-GAL4DBD (#60313),
129 tub>QS> (#77125), GH146-FLP (gift of Christopher Potter, JHU), 20C11-FLP (#55766), UAS-
130 ChR2 (gift of Stefan Pulver, St Andrews), VGlut-GAL4 (#60312), 10xQUAS-ChR2 (#52260),
131 QUAS-shibire^{TS} (#30012).

132 Supplementary figures: R19F06-GAL4DBD (#69098), R53D01-GAL4DBD (#69075), VT059695-
133 GAL4DBD (#73750), VT037031-ZpLexADBD (personal stocks, B.J.D.), VT043690-ZpLexADBD
134 (personal stocks, B.J.D.).

135

136 **Immunohistochemistry and confocal imaging**

137 Dissection and immunostaining of adult brains was done as described previously(Riabinina
138 *et al.* 2015). Briefly, on day 1 brains of 5-7 d.o. adult flies were dissected in ice-cold PBS,
139 fixed at RT for 20 mins in 4% PFA in PBS+0.3% Triton (PBT), then washed in PBT at RT for 1.5-
140 6h, blocked in 5% normal goat serum (NGS) in PBT for 30 mins and placed in primary
141 antibody mix at 4°C for 3 nights on a shaker. On day 4, brains were washed in PBT at RT for
142 5-6h and placed in secondary antibody mix for 2 nights at 4°C on a shaker. On day 6, brains
143 were washed in PBT for 5-6h and left overnight in approx. 50µl of Vectashield mounting
144 solution without shaking. On day 7, brains were mounted in Vectashield on a microscope
145 slide. The primary antibody mix contained rabbit anti-GFP (Invitrogen #A11122, 1:100),
146 mouse nc82 (DSHB, 1:25) and 5% NGS in PBT. The secondary antibody mix contained Alexa

147 Fluor 488 goat anti-rabbit (Invitrogen #A11034), Cy3 anti-mouse (Jackson Immunoresearch
148 #115-165-062) and 5% NGS in PBT.

149 Images were acquired as z-stacks using a Leica SP8 upright confocal microscope equipped
150 with HCX IRAPO L25x/0.95W water-immersion objective (Leica, Germany, 506323), at 512 x
151 512 pixel resolution with 1µm z steps. LAS X v3.5.2 software was used for image acquisition.
152 Imaging settings (laser intensity, gain, etc.) were kept identical for groups of images that
153 were compared to one another. Images were processed by taking maximum intensity
154 projection, rotating and re-colouring in FIJI. Images shown are representative of 3-5
155 stainings for every genotype.

156

157 **Whole-animal imaging**

158 Third-instar larvae were placed on a microscope slide and briefly put into a freezer to
159 immobilize them. Images were taken on a Leica MZ10F zoom fluorescent scope equipped
160 with a Leica DFC 420C camera, QImaging LED light source and LAS v.4 software. The white
161 balance was adjusted automatically by taking an image of a white sheet of paper before
162 experimental images. Identical settings were used to take images that are compared to each
163 other. Images shown are representative of 3-5 for every genotype.

164

165 **Quinic acid feeding**

166 For larval experiments, gravid females were allowed to lay eggs in vials containing standard
167 fly medium, supplemented with QA, and larvae remained in the vials until they reached
168 wall-climbing 3rd instar stage. For adult experiments, flies were raised on standard fly

169 medium and were transferred into vials with QA at 2-3 d.o., for 5 days, at which point they
170 were dissected. To make QA stock, 8 g of QA (Sigma #138622) was dissolved in 40 ml ddH₂O
171 and adjusted to pH7 with 5M NaOH, bringing the total stock volume to 50 ml. 1.6ml/vial of
172 this solution was thoroughly mixed into standard fly medium for larval or adult experiments.

173

174 **Luciferase assay**

175 Each experiment assayed 9-30 larvae or 9-15 adult flies per genotype, in groups of three. 3rd
176 instar larvae or 1-2d.o. adult flies were placed in a 1.5 ml Eppendorf tube and stored in -
177 80°C until all samples for a given experiment were collected. A Dual-Luciferase Reporter
178 Assay system (Promega, E1910) was used for the experiments. Samples were homogenised
179 in 200µl of Passive lysis buffer (Promega, E194A) per tube, and kept on ice for at least 10
180 mins. Then the tubes were centrifuged for 5 mins at 13.4k rpm, and supernatant transferred
181 to new tubes. 30µl of supernatant from each tube were mixed with 30µl of Luciferase assay
182 substrate (Promega, E151A), reconstituted in Luciferase assay buffer (Promega, E195A), per
183 well of a 96-well plate and luminescence was measured immediately on a TECAN GENios
184 plate reader, running XFluor 4 macros for Excel. We used 300ms exposure for adult samples
185 and 600ms exposure for larval samples. We collected 3-10 measurements per experiment
186 per genotype. The luciferase luminescence values were normalised by the amount of
187 protein contained in the samples, to account for possible differences in the size of larvae
188 and adults. For protein assay, 1.5ul of supernatant was mixed with 100ul of Protein assay
189 reagent (BioRAD, #500-0006) and light absorbance measured after 20 mins on a FLUOstar
190 Omega platereader (BMG LABTECH), running Omega software v. 1.3. Two independent
191 samples were measured per each supernatant tube. The absorbance values were converted
192 into mg/ml of protein by measuring a calibration curve with BSA dilutions (NEB, #B90015).

193 Each relative luminescence (RL) data point, presented on the graphs (**Fig 1C-D, 2B-C, 3A-B**)
 194 was calculated as follows:

195 $RL = \frac{LuciferaseMeasurement}{DerivedProtein}$, where

196 $DerivedProtein = 30(a(\frac{ProteinMeasurement_1 + ProteinMeasurement_2}{2} -$

197 $BlankMeasurement) + b)$, a and b parameters were obtained from the best linear fit to
 198 the calibration curve, plotted as (*average of 3 calibration measurement for a given dilution*
 199 *of BSA*)-blank measurement vs dilution of BSA in mg/ml. 4-6 independent RL values were
 200 collected per genotype in each experiment. The genotypes are presented in Figures as
 201 mean±SEM and were compared with 1-way ANOVA (larvae) or 2-way ANOVA (adults) with
 202 Sidak's multiple comparisons test.

203 We have observed significant differences between measurement of adult males and
 204 females for some genotypes, arising from a consistently higher amount of protein per adult
 205 female. These differences were never observed for male and female larvae (data not
 206 shown). Thus, we present adult data separately for males and females.

207

208 **Larval whole-cell patch-clamp recordings**

209 Larvae were grown in the dark on standard fly medium, supplemented with 100µl/vial of 0.1M
 210 all trans-retinal (Sigma, #R2500) in 100% EtOH. Recordings were performed at room
 211 temperature (20-22°C). Third-instar larvae were dissected in external saline (in mM: 135 NaCl,
 212 5 KCl, 4 MgCl₂·6H₂O, 2 CaCl₂·2H₂O, 5 N-Tris[hydroxymethyl]methyl-2-aminoethanesulfonic
 213 acid, and 36 sucrose, pH 7.15). The CNS was removed and secured to a Sylgard (Dow-Corning,
 214 Midland, Michigan, USA)-coated cover slip using tissue glue (GLUture; WPI, Hitchin, UK). The
 215 glia surrounding the CNS was partially removed using protease (1% type XIV; Sigma, Dorset,

216 UK) contained in a wide-bore (15 μm) patch pipette. Whole cell recordings were carried out
217 using borosilicate glass electrodes (GC100TF-10; Harvard Apparatus, Edenbridge, UK), fire-
218 polished to resistances of between 10-14 M Ω . The aCC/RP2 motoneurons were identified by
219 soma position within the ventral nerve cord. When needed, cell identity was confirmed after
220 recording by filling with 0.1% Alexa Fluor 488 hydrazide sodium salt (Invitrogen, Carlsbad,
221 California, USA), included in the internal patch saline (in mM: 140 potassium gluconate, 2
222 MgCl₂·6H₂O, 2 EGTA, 5 KCl, and 20 HEPES, pH 7.4). Mecamylamine (1 mM, M9020, Sigma,
223 Dorset, UK) was included in the external saline to block endogenous excitatory cholinergic
224 mediated currents to aCC/RP2 motoneurons and neuronal depolarisation was elicited
225 through UAS-ChR2(Pulver *et al.* 2009) (λ 470 nm, 500ms, light intensity 9.65 mW/cm² before
226 reaching the LUMPlanFI 60x/0.9W Olympus objective) expressed in all motoneurons by VGlut
227 promoter. Recordings were made using a MultiClamp 700B amplifier. Cells were held at -55
228 mV and recordings were sampled at 20 kHz and lowpass filtered at 10 kHz, using pClamp 10.6
229 (Molecular Devices, Sunnyvale, CA). Only neurons with an input resistance of \geq 500 M Ω were
230 accepted for analysis. 8 recordings were taken per cell, average action potential number per
231 500ms light pulse calculated. Data in **Fig 3E** are presented as mean \pm SEM, and were compared
232 with a 1-way ANOVA with Sidak's multiple comparisons test.

233

234 **Larval escape assays**

235 Individual 3rd instar larvae were assayed at RT (20-22C) in a 9cm petri dish that contained a
236 thin layer of 1% agarose to prevent desiccation. The petri dish was placed under the Leica
237 MZ16F zoom fluorescent microscope with Plan 1.0x lens, fluorescent light source and a GFP
238 filter cube (λ 470 nm). Light intensity measured 9.87 mW/cm² when completely zoomed out.
239 Zoom 5 was used for experiments. Larvae were filmed using a uEye UI-233xSE-C camera

240 with uEye Cockpit software, and data was stored in *.avi format. Each larvae was allowed to
241 crawl in the Petri dish for 2 mins, before it was placed for 2 mins into a 113mm² area,
242 illuminated by blue light. Wild-type larvae naturally avoid bright blue light and crawl away,
243 however, larvae with ChR2 expressed in motoneurons (**Fig 3F**) or pan-neuronally (**Fig 3G**) are
244 impaired in their ability to escape. A larva was returned into the blue light area immediately
245 after the larva had completely left the illuminated area. We counted the number of escapes
246 during a 2 min period. 7-15 larvae were assayed per genotype. The data is shown as
247 mean±SEM. The genotypes were compared with 1-way ANOVA with Sidak's multiple
248 comparison test.

249

250 **Adult behavioural assay**

251 Adult male and female 5-7d.o. flies were assayed in groups of 10 (N=4-5 groups per
252 genotype) in clean empty standard fly vials. Flies were placed in a cooled incubator, set to
253 33°C, and video-recorded at 5 fps using a uEye camera UI-233xSE-C, controlled by uEye
254 Cockpit software. The data was stored in *.avi format. The number of flies on the bottom of
255 each vial was manually counted at 30s intervals. The data is shown as mean±SEM, and was
256 analysed with multiple t-tests with Holm-Sidak correction.

257

258 Fly strains, generated in this study, are available from Bloomington *Drosophila* Stock Centre
259 and upon request from the corresponding author. Plasmids, generated in this study, are
260 available upon request from the corresponding author.

261

262 **Results**263 **Quantification of strength of split-QF transactivators**

264 To make the split-QF system compatible with existing split-GAL4 lines, we used the same
 265 leucine zippers (Pfeiffer *et al.* 2010). We attached Zip- to QFDBD and Zip+ to QFAD, defining
 266 the domains as previously reported (Riabinina *et al.* 2015), and expressed these transgenes
 267 under control of the neuronal synaptobrevin promoter *nsyb* (**Fig 1A**), integrating them in
 268 *attp40* (DBD) and *attp2* (AD) sites. We also generated Zip+ - QF2^wAD flies (in *attp2*) that,
 269 similar to QF2^w transactivator (Riabinina *et al.* 2015) (**Fig 1A**), carry a mutated C-terminal
 270 with reduced negative charge and reduced activity. As expected, animals carrying *nsyb*-
 271 *QFDBD* (*attp40*), *nsyb-QFAD* (*attp2*) and *QUAS-mCD8-GFP* showed strong GFP expression
 272 throughout their nervous system (**Fig 1B**). This expression was repressible by *tub-QS* and
 273 inducible by QA (**Fig S1**). Similar, but weaker, expression was observed with *nsyb-QFDBD*
 274 and *nsyb-QF2^wAD* (**Fig 1B**). Both split transactivators appeared to have lower activity than
 275 QF2 and QF2^w (**Fig 1B**).

276 To quantify the relative strength of split transactivators, and to compare QFAD and QF2^wAD
 277 to existing p65AD and GAL4AD, we generated *nsyb-p65AD* (*attp2*) and *nsyb-GAL4AD* (*attp2*)
 278 flies, and expressed UAS-luciferase in larvae and adults (**Fig 1C,D, Tables S1, S2**). We
 279 analysed male and female flies separately due to the significant differences between sexes
 280 that were observed for some genotypes. No such differences were observed for larvae (not
 281 shown). The strength of the QFDBD+QFAD transactivator was 2.2 times ($p < 0.0001$) less than
 282 QF2 in larvae and 1.8-2 times ($p < 0.0001$) less than QF2 in adults. Similarly, QFDBD+QF2^wAD
 283 was 3 times ($p < 0.0001$) weaker than QF2^w in larvae and 1.4-2.6 times weaker in adults
 284 ($p = 0.19$ in females and $p < 0.0001$ in males). While relative expression levels varied between
 285 larvae (non-sexed) and male vs. female adults, QFAD was ~2 times ($p < 0.01$) stronger than

286 QF2^{wAD}, and ~2 times (p<0.0001) weaker than p65AD. The GAL4AD was consistently weak.
 287 *tub-QS* provided strong repression of all original and split QF variants. We quantified the
 288 effect of QA de-repression in larvae only, because QA is effective only in sensory receptor
 289 neurons and the PI neurons in the adult brain (Riabinina et al. 2015), presumably due to
 290 difficulty crossing the glial blood-brain barrier (Edwards and Meinertzhagen 2010). QA
 291 feeding to *tub-QS*, *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-QFAD* (QF2^{wAD}) larvae, that otherwise had very low
 292 expression, resulted in restoration of expression to levels not significantly different from
 293 *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-QFAD* (QF2^{wAD}) larvae (p=0.87 and p=0.62, respectively). In *tub-QS*, *nsyb-*
 294 *QF2* (QF2^w) larvae the expression was restored to 50-60% of unrepressed levels (p<0.0001
 295 and p=0.0031, respectively). These experiments demonstrate that the split-QF is fully
 296 functional, repressible and inducible, due to the strong activity of the QFAD and QF2^{wAD}
 297 activation domains.

298

299 **Quantification of split-QF transactivators, when used with split-GAL4 and split-LexA**

300 Next we asked whether QFAD and QF2^{wAD} may be effectively used together with existing
 301 GAL4DBD lines, to provide a QS-repressible and QA-inducible alternative to the currently
 302 used p65AD. Pan-neuronal expression in larval CNS, driven by *elav-GAL4DBD* and *nsyb-*
 303 *QF2/QF2^{wAD}*, is strong, repressible and inducible (**Fig 2A, top**). To investigate expression in
 304 the adult brain, we used *GAL4DBD* lines from the Janelia and Vienna collections in
 305 combination with *nsyb-QFAD* and *nsyb-QF2^{wAD}* to drive GFP expression in antennal lobe
 306 (AL), suboesophageal zone (SEZ), antennal mechanosensory and motor centre (AMMC),
 307 optic lobes (OL) and sparsely in other areas of the brain (**Fig 2A, bottom** and **Fig S2**). The
 308 observed expression was strong and repressible in all neurons in the predicted expression
 309 patterns, and QA-inducible in the olfactory and gustatory receptor neurons, as observed

310 previously with *nsyb-QF2* (Riabinina et al. 2015). To quantify the strength of expression, we
 311 used *elav-GAL4DBD* in combination with the AD variants to drive luciferase in the CNS of 3rd
 312 instar larvae, however, the *elav-GAL4DBD, nsyb-p65AD* combination was lethal (**Fig 2B and**
 313 **Table S3**). Similarly to experiments in **Fig 1C**, QFAD-induced expression was not significantly
 314 different from QF2^wAD ($p=0.16$). In contrary to experiments with split-QF (**Fig. 1C**), here QA
 315 resulted in restoration of expression to ~20-35% of that of the un-repressed split
 316 transactivators ($p<0.0001$). Similarly to QF2 and QF2^w, QA feeding restored expression levels
 317 of *tub-QS, nsyb-GAL4QF* to 60% of the un-repressed levels ($p<0.0001$). To quantify expression
 318 levels in the adult CNS, we used *ChAT-GAL4DBD* to target cholinergic neurons and to avoid
 319 larval lethality, previously observed with *elav-GAL4DBD, nsyb-p65AD* (**Fig 2C, Table S4**).
 320 QFAD-driven expression was comparable with QF2^wAD ($p>0.99$) and ~4 times weaker than
 321 p65AD ($p<0.0001$). As previously observed (e.g. **Fig 1C,D**), *tub-QS* provided strong
 322 repression, not different from DBD-only or AD-only controls ($p>0.99$). These experiments
 323 demonstrate that QFAD and QF2^wAD activation domains may be used together with
 324 GAL4DBD lines to provide a repressible and inducible, albeit weaker, alternative to p65AD.
 325 The QFAD and QF2^wAD activation domains also work with split-LexA reagents in larval and
 326 adult CNS (**Fig 2D, Figure S3**). Moreover, expression is again both repressible and QA-
 327 inducible. Although we did not quantify strength of expression by luciferase assay (due to
 328 the unavailability of a LexAop-Luc reporter), it appears that QF2^wAD domain works as well,
 329 or better, than QFAD in these experiments.

330

331 **Applications of split-QF**

332 First, we asked how the QS repression compares with Killer-Zipper (Dolan *et al.* 2017), a tool
333 that silences split-GAL4 expression by driving GAL4DBD-Zip+ construct with the
334 LexA/LexAop system (**Fig 3A, B, Table S5**). We observed that QS-induced repression was
335 stronger ($p=0.0071$ for *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-QFAD*, *KZip* vs *tub-QS*, *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-QFAD*
336 females) or the same (all other genotypes, $p>0.83$) as a Killer-Zipper-induced equivalent. The
337 use of QS for repression is thus more advantageous than Killer-Zipper because it requires
338 fewer transgenes and does not recruit the LexA/LexAop system. In addition, the mechanism
339 of QS repression is different from that of Killer-Zipper, that is based on competitive
340 dimerization between GAL4DBD-Zip+ and GAL4DBD-Zip- components.

341 Next, we tested whether the split-QF system may be effectively used for simultaneous
342 expression of UAS and LexAop transgenes, and for advanced intersectional expression. We
343 confirmed that a *QF2^{wAD}* domain, when combined with *GAL4DBD* or *ZpLexADBBD*, drives
344 simultaneous expression from both *UAS-RFP* and the *LexAop-GFP* reporters in both larvae
345 and adult (**Fig 3C**). For advanced intersectional experiments, we regulated expression of QS
346 via the FLP-FRT system that, in turn, controlled the split-transactivators. As expected,
347 intersection of *Chat-GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-QF2^{wAD}* and *GH146-FLP* resulted in strong labelling of
348 cholinergic olfactory projection neurons (**Fig 3D, left**). No labelling was observed when *Chat-*
349 *GAL4DBD* was replaced by a glutamatergic driver *VGlut-GAL4DBD* (not shown). Similarly, we
350 observed expression throughout the brain and in optic lobes in the cholinergic, but not
351 glutamatergic (not shown), neurons that are targeted by *20C11-FLP* (Chen *et al.* 2014) (**Fig**
352 **3D, middle**). Interestingly, intersection of *VT009847-ZpLexADBBD*, *nsyb-QFAD* and *20C11-FLP*
353 resulted in labelling only one SEZ neuron (**Fig 3D, right**). These experiments demonstrate
354 that split-QF can effectively achieve simultaneous and intersectional expression, narrowing
355 down expression patterns of split-GAL4, split-LexA and FLP lines.

356

357 Finally, we applied the split-QF system to study physiology and behaviour in *Drosophila*. To
 358 explore the usability of GAL4DBD + QFAD for electrophysiology, we performed whole-cell
 359 patch-clamp recordings from aCC and RP2 motoneurons of third-instar larvae. Neuronal
 360 depolarisation was evoked through activation of UAS-ChR2 (Pulver *et al.* 2009) expressed in
 361 all motoneurons by *VGlut-GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-QF2^{wAD}* or, in controls, *VGlut-GAL4* (**Fig 3E, Table**
 362 **S6**). The number of action potentials produced from *VGlut-GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-QF2^{wAD}* larvae
 363 (42 ± 6 per 500ms) was not different from that observed in the GAL4 controls (51 ± 6 ,
 364 $p=0.62$). QS completely eliminated ChR2-induced depolarization in *tub-QS, VGlut-GAL4DBD*,
 365 *nsyb-QF2^{wAD}* larvae (**Fig 3E**), while feeding larvae of the same genotype with QA partially
 366 restored depolarization and action potential count (10 ± 5), but to a level significantly below
 367 the unrepressed levels of *VGlut-GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-QF2^{wAD}* larvae ($p=0.0016$). These readouts
 368 of cellular activity are paralleled by behavioural phenotypes. We counted how many times
 369 (in 2 mins) larvae of these 4 genotypes escaped a blue light area (**Fig 3F, Table S6**). As
 370 expected, larvae containing the QS transgene escaped most readily (11 ± 1.8 escapes), while
 371 feeding larvae with QA significantly reduced the number of escapes to 9.3 ± 1.3 ($p=0.038$),
 372 due to the seizure-like neuronal activity, elicited by ChR2 activation. *VGlut-GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-*
 373 *QF2^{wAD}* were also able to escape (5.9 ± 0.6), but significantly less than the QS larvae
 374 ($p<0.0001$). *VGlut-GAL4* control larvae were unable to escape (0.2 ± 0.1).

375 We used the same assay to measure larval escape following activation of ChR2 driven pan-
 376 neuronally by split-QF (**Fig 3G, Table S7**). Abolished mobility was observed in larvae that
 377 expressed ChR2 (0 ± 0 escapes in *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-QFAD* and *nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^{wAD}*
 378 larvae), and in larvae that expressed QS fed with QA (0.3 ± 0.2 and 0.1 ± 0.1 escapes for

379 QFAD and QF2^{wAD}, respectively). By contrast, QS-expressing larvae not fed with QA readily
 380 escaped the blue light area (7.4 ± 0.7 and 8.0 ± 0.8 escapes, respectively).

381 We also assayed adult flies with pan-neuronal expression of *shibire*^{TS} (Fig 3H, Table S8).

382 When placed at 33°C, *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-QFAD* flies became gradually paralysed as
 383 expected. The same effect was observed in *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-QF2^{wAD}* flies, but took longer
 384 to develop, presumably due to the lower expression levels of *shibire*^{TS}. When the expression
 385 of *shibire*^{TS} was suppressed by *tub-QS*, no paralysis was observed.

386 Collectively, these experiments demonstrate that split-QF may be used with or without split-
 387 GAL4 to direct expression of effectors in electrophysiological and behavioural assays.

388

389 Discussion

390 Here we demonstrate the use of split-QF by itself, or in combinations with split-GAL4 and
 391 split-LexA, for advanced intersectional experiments, concurrent independent use of UAS and
 392 LexAop transactivators, electrophysiology, optogenetics and thermogenetics in *Drosophila*.
 393 Ultimately, split-QF facilitates targeting of small populations of cells, and may be used for
 394 neuronal connectomics analysis or to explore behavioural phenotypes that are produced by
 395 artificial activation of single neurons. The absence of large libraries of split-QF lines is
 396 currently limiting, but these lines may be generated from split-GAL4 and split-LexA stocks
 397 by, for example, the HACK method (Lin and Potter 2016).

398

399 Quantification of transactivator activity

400 Three factors likely contribute to the lower strength of split transactivators when compared
401 to the full-length ones (**Fig 1C, D** and **2B, C**). First, the *nsyb-QFDBD* transgene has been
402 integrated into the *attp40* site, which may be weaker than *attp2*, where the full
403 transactivators are integrated. Second, the binding between QFDBD and QFAD (QF2^wAD) is a
404 process with a probability <1, which is predicted to result in a lower number of
405 reconstituted split transactivators compared to full-length ones. Consistent with this idea,
406 the reporter expression by split transactivators appeared to be more variable than normally
407 observed with full-length transactivators. Third, it is possible that the spatial configuration
408 of the reconstituted QFDBD + QFAD (QF2^wAD) is somewhat different and less efficient than
409 the full-length QF2 (QF2^w). Reduction of the transactivator strength is assessed by the
410 expression level of reporters, which directly translates into the number of labelled cells as
411 low levels of reporter expression could render some cells undetectable.

412 The luciferase and electrophysiology readouts of QA-fed GAL4DBD+QFAD/QF2^wAD larvae
413 were significantly below the non-suppressed GAL4DBD+QFAD/QF2^wAD (**Fig 2B** and **Fig 3E**).

414 On the other hand, GFP readouts of QA-fed LexADBBD+QFAD/QF2^wAD larvae and adults
415 appear to be equal to the unrepressed LexADBBD+QFAD/QF2^wAD (**Fig 2D**). These results,
416 combined with the split-QF data (**Fig 1C**), indicate that the strength of QS binding to QFAD
417 may be affected by the overall conformation of the reconstituted transactivator,
418 subsequently resulting in different QA efficiency.

419

420 **Use of split-QF beyond *Drosophila***

421 The first use of split-QF was reported in *C.elegans* (Wei et al. 2012), albeit in a different
422 form, including a QF dimerization domain, and without detailed characterisation of QS and

423 QA effects. Experiments presented here indicate that QF2^{wAD}, QS and QA are likely to be
424 functional in *C.elegans* and can extend the use of split-QF in this organism.

425 The Q-system works well across species. It has recently been introduced into zebrafish
426 (Subedi et al. 2014) and malaria mosquitoes (Riabinina et al. 2016), dramatically expanding
427 the very limited set of tools for transgene expression in mosquito. Split-QF may thus be a
428 very useful addition to the genetic toolkit of these two organisms. Considering progressively
429 wider use of genetic tools in other arthropods, such as moths (Long et al. 2015), beetles
430 (Rylee et al. 2018), locust (Wang et al. 2018), ants (Yan et al. 2017) and bees (Schulte et al.
431 2014), and in plants (Bruce et al. 2015), the split-QF and the Q-system may be the tools of
432 choice in these organisms as well.

433

434 In summary, we present a split-QF system that is applicable for advanced anatomical,
435 behavioural and physiological manipulations in *Drosophila*. This system is fully compatible
436 and complementary with the existing split-GAL4 and split-LexA lines and can greatly expand
437 their use by making them QS-repressible and QA-inducible. In addition, combinations of
438 split-QF with split-GAL4 and split-LexA systems can make extensive use of the available UAS
439 and LexAop reporters.

440

441

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450

451 **Author contributions**

452 OR conceived of the project and designed most of the experiments. SWV and RB designed
453 the electrophysiology experiments. OR and SWV performed the experiments. BJD provided
454 unpublished reagents and suggestions. RB provided access to equipment and reagents. All
455 authors contributed to drafting and revisions of the manuscript.

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535

536

537 **Figures**

Figure 1

538

539 **Figure 1. Quantification and validation of split-QF reagents. A.** Schematics of the split-QF

540 system. **B.** Pan-neuronal expression of GFP in larval (top; scale bar, 200μm) and adult

541 (bottom; scale bar, 50μm) CNS by split-QF (first four columns) and Q-system (last four

542 columns). **C, D.** Quantification of split-Q transactivators in larval (**C**) and adult (**D**) CNS by a

543 luciferase assay. All split and full-length transactivators were driven by *nsvb*, while QS was

544 driven by *tubulin*. Green data points show quantification for *nsvb*-*QFDBD*, *QUAS*-*luc*; *nsvb*-

545 *QFAD*, *QUAS*-*luc* and *nsvb*-*QF2^{AD}*, *QUAS*-*luc* controls.

546

Figure 2

547

548 **Figure 2. split-QF, split-GAL4 and split-LexA.** **A, top.** Expression of GFP in larval CNS, driven
 549 by *elav-GAL4DBD* and *nsyb-QFAD* (3 left columns) or *nsyb-QF2^{AD}* (three right columns).
 550 Second and fifth columns show *tub-QS*-induced repression. Third and sixth columns show
 551 recovery of expression in larvae, grown on food with quinic acid. Scale bar, 200µm. **A, bottom.**

552 Same as top, but driven by *VT019838-GAL4DBD* in adult CNS. Adults were fed with quinic acid
553 for 5 days. Scale bar, 50 μ m. **B.** Quantification of relative strength of chimeric split
554 transactivator in larval CNS. Genotypes were *elav-GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-QFAD* (red) or *elav-*
555 *GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-QF2^wAD* (blue) without (right) or with (middle) *tub-QS* and QA treatment
556 (right). *elav-GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-GAL4AD* larvae (grey) had very low luciferase levels, while *elav-*
557 *GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-p65AD* larvae did not survive. Purple bars show data from *nsyb-GAL4QF*
558 larvae for comparison. **C.** Same as **B**, but in adult CNS. Males and females are quantified
559 separately due to significantly different expression levels. Green data points show
560 quantification for *elav-GAL4DBD*, *UAS-luc*; *nsyb-QFAD*, *UAS-luc* and *nsyb-QF2^wAD*, *UAS-luc*
561 controls. **D, top.** Expression of GFP in larval CNS, driven by *VT007395-LexADBD* and *nsyb-*
562 *QFAD* (3 left columns) or *nsyb-QF2^wAD* (three right columns). Second and fifth columns show
563 *tub-QS* induced repression. Third and sixth columns show recovery of expression in the larvae,
564 grown on food with quinic acid. Scale bar, 200 μ m. **D, bottom.** Same as top, but driven by
565 *VT009847-LexADBD* in adult CNS. Adults were fed with quinic acid for 5 days. Scale bars,
566 50 μ m.

567

Figure 3

568

569 **Figure 3. Applications of split-QF.** A, B. Repression of expression by *Killer-Zipper* (Dolan et

570 al. 2017) or *tub-QS*. Expression levels were quantified in adult flies using a luciferase assay.

571 Genotypes of flies without repression were *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-QFAD*, *QUAS-Luc* (**A, right**) or
 572 *elav-GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-QFAD*, *UAS-Luc* (**B, right**). Killer-Zipper flies were *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-*
 573 *QFAD*, *nsyb-LexAQF*, *lexAop-KZip+*, *QUAS-Luc* (**A, middle, green**) or *elav-GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-*
 574 *QFAD*, *nsyb-LexAQF*, *lexAop-KZip+*, *UAS-Luc* (**B, middle, green**). QS flies were *tub-QS*, *nsyb-*
 575 *QFDBD*, *nsyb-QFAD*, *QUAS-Luc* (**A, left**) or *tub-QS*, *elav-GAL4DBD*, *nsyb-QFAD*, *UAS-Luc* (**B,**
 576 **left**). **C.** Simultaneous expression of RFP and GFP in independent neuronal subpopulations in
 577 larvae (left; scale bar, 200µm.) and adult (right; scale bar, 50µm) by *QF2^{wAD}* forming
 578 functional transactivators with *GAL4DBD* and *LexADBD*. **D.** Intersectional expression,
 579 enabled by QS-repressible *GAL4DBD+QF/QF2^{wAD}* and *LexADBD+QFAD* transactivators. GFP
 580 is expressed only in cells that 1) are expressing FLP or are progeny of cells that were
 581 expressing FLP; 2) are expressing G4DBD or LexADBD; 3) are expressing QFAD or QF2^{wAD}.
 582 Third panel from the left shows a zoomed-in image of the z-stack of the brain, shown on the
 583 second panel. Scale bars, 50µm. **E.** Whole-cell patch-clamp recordings from aCC/PR2
 584 motoneurons in third instar larvae of indicated genotypes, raised on food, supplemented
 585 with all-trans retinal. Depolarisation was elicited by blue light. Example traces are shown on
 586 the right. Scale Bars (Traces: 10mV/100ms, Stimulus: 2V/100ms). **F.** Escape assay of larvae
 587 with the same genotypes as in **E.** Each larva was given 2 mins to escape from a 113 mm²
 588 area, lit by blue light (λ470 nm). Once the larva has completely left the lit area, it was
 589 returned into the area. **G.** Escape assay of *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-QFAD* larvae (red) and *nsyb-*
 590 *QFDBD*, *nsyb-QF2^{wAD}* larvae (blue) with or without *tub-QS* and QA. **H.** Adult *nsyb-QFDBD*,
 591 *nsyb-QFAD*, *QUAS-shi^{7S}* (red diamonds) and *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-QF2^{wAD}*, *QUAS-shi^{7S}* (dark
 592 blue upward triangles) flies were paralysed when placed in 33°C incubator at t=0 min. Flies
 593 that also had a *tub-QS* transgene (yellow squares and light-blue downward triangles) were
 594 not paralysed. The data shows the average number of flies (out of 10, ±SEM) at the bottom
 595 of the vial over time. Each graph is an average of n=5 repeats, apart from “QF2^{wAD}+QS”,

596 with n=4. Red dot and blue dot indicate the time point when the corresponding genotypes
597 with and without QS became significantly different for the first time (t-test with Holm-Sidak
598 correction for multiple comparisons). Stars indicate data points where *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-*
599 *QFAD*, *QUAS-shi^{TS}* and *nsyb-QFDBD*, *nsyb-QF2^{wAD}*, *QUAS-shi^{TS}* flies performed significantly
600 differently (t-test with Holm-Sidak correction for multiple comparisons).

601

602 **Supplementary material for Riabinina et al, 2019**

603

Figure S1

604

605 **Figure S1. Quantification and validation of split-QF reagents.** Pan-neuronal expression of
 606 GFP in the larval CNS by split-QF. Panels 1,2, 4 and 5 are the same as in Fig 1. Panels 3 and 6
 607 show QA-induced de-repression. Scale bars, 200µm.

608

Figure S2

609

610 **Figure S2. split-QF and split-GAL4.** Expression of GFP in adult CNS, driven by *R19F06-*
 611 *GAL4DBD* (top), *R53D01-GAL4DBD* (middle), *VT059695-GAL4DBD* (bottom) and *nsyb-QFAD*
 612 (3 left columns) or *nsyb-QF2^wAD* (three right columns). Second and fifth columns show *tub-*
 613 *QS*-induced repression. Third and sixth columns show recovery of expression in adults that
 614 were fed quinic acid for 5 days. Scale bar, 50µm.

Figure S3

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Figure S3. split-QF and split-LexA. Expression of GFP in adult CNS, driven by VT007395-*LexADBBD* (top), VT037023-*LexADBBD* (middle), VT043690-*LexADBBD* (bottom) and *nsyb-QFAD* (3 left columns) or *nsyb-QF2^{wAD}* (three right columns). Second and fifth columns show *tub-QS*-induced repression. Third and sixth columns show recovery of expression in adults that were fed quinic acid for 5 days. Scale bar, 50µm.

622 **Table S1. Quantification of expression strength of split-QF reagents in larvae**

Larval genotype	Relative luciferase activity, mean±SEM	N
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	341 ± 17	10
<i>tub-QS,nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	15 ± 1	8
<i>tub-QS,nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc + QA</i>	266 ± 61	5
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	143 ± 33	10
<i>tub-QS,nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	10 ± 1	10
<i>tub-QS,nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-Luc + QA</i>	221 ± 29	10
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-p65AD, QUAS-Luc</i>	654 ± 42	6
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-GAL4AD, QUAS-Luc</i>	24 ± 4	5
<i>nsyb-QF2, QUAS-Luc</i>	767 ± 91	5
<i>tub-QS,nsyb-QF2, QUAS-Luc</i>	20 ± 2	5
<i>tub-QS,nsyb-QF2, QUAS-Luc + QA</i>	376 ± 75	6
<i>nsyb-QF2^w, QUAS-Luc</i>	431 ± 55	10
<i>tub-QS,nsyb-QF2^w, QUAS-Luc</i>	11 ± 1	10
<i>tub-QS,nsyb-QF2^w, QUAS-Luc + QA</i>	258 ± 33	10

623

624
625**Table S2. Quantification of expression strength of split-QF reagents in adults**

Adult genotype	Relative luciferase activity, mean±SEM	N
<u>Females</u>		
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	1076 ± 72	5
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	60 ± 3	5
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	681 ± 40	5
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	35 ± 2	5
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-p65AD, QUAS-Luc</i>	1719 ± 74	5
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-GAL4AD, QUAS-Luc</i>	30 ± 1	5
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, QUAS-Luc</i>	36 ± 1	5
<i>nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	25 ± 1	5
<i>nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	23 ± 1	5
<i>nsyb-QF2, QUAS-Luc</i>	2207 ± 150	5
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QF2, QUAS-Luc</i>	51 ± 23	5
<i>nsyb-QF2^w, QUAS-Luc</i>	973 ± 63	5
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QF2^w, QUAS-Luc</i>	58 ± 2	5
<u>Males</u>		
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	1337 ± 71	5
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	61 ± 1	3
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	670 ± 37	4
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	73 ± 13	4
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-p65AD, QUAS-Luc</i>	2667 ± 202	5
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-GAL4AD, QUAS-Luc</i>	54 ± 1	5
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, QUAS-Luc</i>	64 ± 4	5
<i>nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	67 ± 4	5
<i>nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	45 ± 2	5
<i>nsyb-QF2, QUAS-Luc</i>	2410 ± 167	4
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QF2, QUAS-Luc</i>	90 ± 3	5
<i>nsyb-QF2^w, QUAS-Luc</i>	1764 ± 95	5
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QF2^w, QUAS-Luc</i>	83 ± 2	5

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627 **Table S3. Quantification of expression strength of split-QF + split-GAL4 reagents in larvae**

Larval genotype	Relative luciferase activity, mean±SEM	N
<i>elav-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	213 ± 16	6
<i>tub-QS, elav-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	1.4 ± 0.1	3
<i>tub-QS, elav-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc + QA</i>	44 ± 9	5
<i>elav-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-Luc</i>	167 ± 12	6
<i>tub-QS, elav-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-Luc</i>	1.6 ± 0.1	6
<i>tub-QS, elav-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-Luc + QA</i>	60 ± 5	5
<i>elav-GAL4DBD, nsyb-p65AD, UAS-Luc</i>	lethal	0
<i>elav-GAL4DBD, nsyb-GAL4AD, UAS-Luc</i>	9 ± 1	6
<i>nsyb-GAL4QF, UAS-Luc</i>	319 ± 10	6
<i>tub-QS,nsyb-GAL4QF, UAS-Luc</i>	2.5 ± 0.2	6
<i>tub-QS,nsyb- GAL4QF, UAS-Luc + QA</i>	199 ± 21	6

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629 **Table S4. Quantification of expression strength of split-QF + split-GAL4 reagents in adults**

Adult genotype	Relative luciferase activity, mean±SEM	N
<u>Females</u>		
<i>ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	488 ± 50	5
<i>tub-QS, ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	10 ± 3	5
<i>ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-Luc</i>	366 ± 8	5
<i>tub-QS, ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-Luc</i>	6 ± 1	5
<i>ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-p65AD, UAS-Luc</i>	1763 ± 217	5
<i>ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-GAL4AD, UAS-Luc</i>	12 ± 4	5
<i>ChAT-GAL4DBD, UAS-Luc</i>	4.2 ± 0.6	5
<i>nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	8 ± 2	5
<i>nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-Luc</i>	2.8 ± 0.4	5
<i>nsyb-GAL4QF, UAS-Luc</i>	798 ± 274	5
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-GAL4QF, UAS-Luc</i>	16 ± 2	5
<u>Males</u>		
<i>ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	606 ± 56	5
<i>tub-QS, ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	15 ± 1	5
<i>ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-Luc</i>	459 ± 6	5
<i>tub-QS, ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-Luc</i>	6.3 ± 0.3	5
<i>ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-p65AD, UAS-Luc</i>	2803 ± 330	5
<i>ChAT-GAL4DBD, nsyb-GAL4AD, UAS-Luc</i>	27 ± 2	5
<i>ChAT-GAL4DBD, UAS-Luc</i>	5.8 ± 0.7	5
<i>nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	6.3 ± 0.7	5
<i>nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-Luc</i>	8 ± 3	5
<i>nsyb-GAL4QF, UAS-Luc</i>	1377 ± 139	5
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-GAL4QF, UAS-Luc</i>	12 ± 1	5

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631 **Table S5. Quantification of repression by QS and KZip⁺**

Adult genotype	Relative luciferase activity, mean±SEM	Repression, fold	N
<u>Females</u>			
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	823 ± 70		5
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, nsyb-LexAQF, lexAop-KZip+, QUAS-Luc</i>	226 ± 18	3.6	4
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	52 ± 10	15.8	5
<i>elav-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	737 ± 93		5
<i>elav-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, nsyb-LexAQF, lexAop-KZip+, UAS-Luc</i>	61 ± 32	12	5
<i>tub-QS, elav-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	17 ± 2	43	5
<u>Males</u>			
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	818 ± 30		5
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, nsyb-LexAQF, lexAop-KZip+, QUAS-Luc</i>	99 ± 16	8.3	5
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-Luc</i>	61 ± 3	13.4	4
<i>elav-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	1464 ± 46		5
<i>elav-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, nsyb-LexAQF, lexAop-KZip+, UAS-Luc</i>	56 ± 13	26	5
<i>tub-QS, elav-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, UAS-Luc</i>	36 ± 4	41	5

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633 **Table S6. Optogenetic experiments in GAL4DBD + QF2^wAD larvae**

Genotype	Number of spikes	N	Number of escapes	N
<i>VGlut-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-ChR2</i>	43 ± 6	7	5.9 ± 0.6	10
<i>tub-QS, VGlut-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-ChR2</i>	0 ± 0	5	11.1 ± 0.5	15
<i>tub-QS, VGlut-GAL4DBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, UAS-ChR2 + QA</i>	10 ± 5	7	9.3 ± 0.4	10
<i>VGlut-GAL4, UAS-ChR2</i>	51 ± 6	7	0.2 ± 0.1	10

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635 **Table S7. Optogenetic experiments in split-QF larvae**

Genotype	Number of escapes	N
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-ChR2</i>	0 ± 0	10
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-ChR2</i>	7.4 ± 0.7	10
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-ChR2 + QA</i>	0.3 ± 0.2	10
<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-ChR2</i>	0 ± 0	10
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-ChR2</i>	8 ± 0.8	7
<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^wAD, QUAS-ChR2 + QA</i>	0.1 ± 0.1	9

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637 **Table S8. Thermogenetic experiments in split-QF adults**

Time, min	Number of flies on the bottom of the vial			
	<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-shibire^{TS}</i> (N=5)	<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QFAD, QUAS-shibire^{TS}</i> (N=4)	<i>nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^{wAD}, QUAS-shibire^{TS}</i> (N=5)	<i>tub-QS, nsyb-QFDBD, nsyb-QF2^{wAD}, QUAS-shibire^{TS}</i> (N=4)
0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0.2 ± 0.2	0 ± 0
0.5	0.4 ± 0.2	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0
1	0.4 ± 0.2	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0
1.5	0.6 ± 0.4	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0.5 ± 0.3
2	1.2 ± 0.6	0 ± 0	0.2 ± 0.2	0.25 ± 0.25
2.5	1.6 ± 0.8	0 ± 0	0.2 ± 0.2	0.25 ± 0.25
3	1.8 ± 0.8	0 ± 0	0.8 ± 0.6	0.25 ± 0.25
3.5	2.4 ± 1.1	0 ± 0	0.8 ± 0.6	0.5 ± 0.3
4	3.2 ± 1.2	0 ± 0	1 ± 0.5	0.75 ± 0.25
4.5	3.6 ± 1.3	0 ± 0	1.4 ± 0.7	0.75 ± 0.25
5	4 ± 1.3	0 ± 0	1.2 ± 0.7	0.75 ± 0.25
5.5	4.4 ± 1.4	0.25 ± 0.25	1.6 ± 0.7	0.5 ± 0.3
6	4.2 ± 1.4	0.25 ± 0.25	2 ± 0.7	0.75 ± 0.25
6.5	5.8 ± 1.4	0.25 ± 0.25	3 ± 1.2	1 ± 0.4
7	7 ± 1	0.25 ± 0.25	3 ± 1.4	0.5 ± 0.3
7.5	7.4 ± 0.8	0.25 ± 0.25	3.6 ± 1.3	0.5 ± 0.3
8	7.8 ± 0.7	0 ± 0	3.8 ± 1.3	0.5 ± 0.3
8.5	9 ± 0.5	0.25 ± 0.25	4.8 ± 1	0.5 ± 0.3
9	9.4 ± 0.2	0 ± 0	5.2 ± 1.3	0.75 ± 0.5
9.5	9.8 ± 0.2	0 ± 0	5.8 ± 1	0.75 ± 0.5
10	9.8 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.5	6.4 ± 1	1.3 ± 0.9
10.5	9.8 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.5	7.4 ± 1	1 ± 1
11	10 ± 0	0.25 ± 0.25	8 ± 0.6	0.5 ± 0.3
11.5	10 ± 0	0 ± 0	8.2 ± 0.7	0.25 ± 0.25
12	10 ± 0	0 ± 0	8.4 ± 0.7	0.3 ± 0.3
12.5	10 ± 0	0 ± 0	8.8 ± 0.5	0 ± 0
13	10 ± 0	0 ± 0	9.2 ± 0.5	0 ± 0
13.5	10 ± 0	0 ± 0	9.4 ± .4	0 ± 0
14	10 ± 0	0 ± 0	9.2 ± 0.5	0 ± 0
14.5	10 ± 0	0 ± 0	9.8 ± 0.2	0 ± 0
15	10 ± 0	0 ± 0	10 ± 0	0 ± 0

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